

DEVELOP WEAR-RESISTANT POLYMERIC COMPOSITES BY USING NANOPARTICLES

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1 Abstract

In the present work, the role of the nanoparticle fillers on the sliding wear behaviour of hybrid polymeric composites was investigated. It was found that additional nanoparticles could further enhance the wear resistance of polymer composites, especially under extreme sliding conditions. The beneficial effect of nanoparticles was mainly attributed to the reduction in the adhesion between the transfer film and the polymeric specimen, which helped the formation of continuous transfer film and consequently protected the fibers from severe abrasive wear. The concept allows the development of the new wear-resistant hybrid polymeric composites by blending nanoparticles with traditional tribo-fillers.

2 Introduction

Over the past decades, polymer composites have been increasingly applied as structural materials in the aerospace, automotive, and chemical industries, providing lower weight alternatives to metallic materials. A number of these applications are concentrated on tribological components, such as gears, cams, bearings and seals, where the self-lubrication of polymers is of special advantage [1, 2]. To overcome the inhibited weakness of polymers, various fillers such as short carbon fibers and graphite flakes have been used to develop polymer composites for high wear resistance [1]. In particular, short fiber-reinforced polymers (SFRPs) have formed an important class of tribo-materials owing to their high specific strength, good load-carrying capacity and rapid, lower-cost processibility. Recently, with the booming of nanophased materials, nano-sized inorganic particles have also come under consideration. In particular, it

was found that the combination of nanoparticles with conventional micro-sized fillers can achieve a synergistic effect on the tribological behavior of polymeric materials [3, 4].

In the present work, attempts were made to develop wear resistant polymeric hybrid nanocomposites, by using both nanoparticles and conventional micro-sized tribo-fillers. It was found that the additional nanoparticles could effectively enhance the wear resistance of polymer composites, especially under extreme sliding conditions. On the basis of microscopic observations of worn surfaces, the wear mechanisms were discussed. The tribological role of nanoparticle in modifying the sliding wear behavior of polymer composites was particularly studied.

3 Materials and Experimental

2.1 Materials

Two kinds of polymers, i.e. epoxy (EP) and polyamide 66 (PA 66), were used as matrices, and the short carbon fiber (SCF) and two solid lubricants i.e. graphite and PTFE, acted as conventional tribo-fillers. The average diameter of SCF was $\sim 14.5 \mu\text{m}$, with an average fiber length of $\sim 90 \mu\text{m}$. The size of the graphite flakes and the PTFE powder particles amounted to $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. Nano-sized TiO_2 particles were used as the additional filler, at a volume content of 5%. The average diameter of the particles was 300 nm. Technical details of the fillers and matrix, as well as the compositions and the compounding procedure have been reported previously [5, 6]. In terms of the epoxy composites, a composition of 15vol%SCF + 5vol%graphite + 5vol%PTFE was used as a benchmark for the conventional polymeric composites, which was formulated as the optimum content according to the results from a series of SCF/graphite/PTFE/epoxy-based composites [8].

For the PA 66 composites, a composition of 15vol%SCF + 5vol%graphite was used as the conventional SFRP composite.

2.2 Wear Tests

The wear tests were performed on a pin-on-disc apparatus [5]. The specimen pin ($4 \times 4 \times 12 \text{ mm}^3$) was rotated against a polished steel disc, with an initial surface roughness Ra, of $\sim 220 \text{ nm}$. All tests in this study were conducted under dry condition at room temperature. During the test, the friction coefficient was recorded and calculated by the ratio between tangential force and normal load. The reduction in specimen's height was measured by a displacement transducer, which could be used to characterize the development of the wear process. An additional monitoring of the temperature rise during testing was carried out by an iron-constantan thermocouple positioned on the edge of the steel disc. After the test, the mass loss of the specimen was measured for the calculation of the specific wear rate i.e. the most important tribological property of the material, by using the equation

$$w_s = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho F_N L} \quad [\text{mm}^3/\text{Nm}] \quad (1)$$

where Δm is the specimen's mass loss, ρ is the density of the specimen, F_N is the normal load applied on the specimen during sliding, and L is the total sliding distance.

3 Wear Tests Results

Figure 1a summarizes the wear test results of the polymeric composites in comparison with that of the pure polymers. The applied tribo-fillers enhanced the wear resistance of the polymers by about one order of magnitude at 1 MPa, 1 m/s. In this case, it is also noticed that the wear rates of the SFRP composites are in the range of $10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$, which is in agreement with results typically found for SFRPs sliding against various steel counterfaces [7]. With an increase in pv , the wear rate of the composites filled with traditional fillers progressively increased, suggesting changes in the dominant wear mechanisms. For the composite with additional nanoparticles, however, the wear rate of the nanocomposite was relatively stable at $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$, even under high pv conditions. This means that the limiting pv of the nanocomposite was

clearly improved, which would promote the use of these materials for tribo-applications in which more severe wear conditions are dominant.

Figure 1b compares the friction coefficient of the specimens tested under different sliding conditions. It was found that the addition of nanoparticles could effectively reduce the friction coefficient of SFRPs under all the testing conditions applied here. There is, however, no general relationship between the trends in friction coefficient and specific wear rate as a function of pv -product. Nevertheless, a high friction force/coefficient is normally undesirable for polymeric materials, not only because it may accelerate the wear loss of the materials, but it also will lead to a high contact temperature due to the frictional heating, and thus a thermal-mechanical failure of the material. In the following sections, the wear mechanisms of SFRP composites will be further discussed based on microscopic observations. In particular, the mechanisms for the favorable effects of nanoparticles on the wear behavior of SFRPs will be discussed in more detail.

4 Analysis of Wear Mechanisms

It is known that the wear performance of SFRP composites is to a great extent determined by the properties of the fibers [7]. This is also true for hybrid SFRP composites filled with additional particulate fillers, such as the materials considered in this study. Figure 2 shows the microscopic view of fibers exposed on the worn surfaces of epoxy based SFRP composites filled without and with nanoparticles. It can be observed that the fibers clearly stand out from the polymeric matrix and are fully exposed to the counterparts. By using an atomic force microscopy (AFM), the height from the matrix surface to the exposed fiber can be accurately measured. It was found that the height of the exposed fiber always agreed with the original surface roughness of the steel counterpart (which is $\sim 220 \text{ nm}$) [6]. Hence, during the wear process, the short fibers had to carry most of the load. To fully explore the strengthening effect of short fibers, it is critical to ensure that the fibers are only gradually removed from the polymer matrix i.e. without serious breakage.

On the basis of the above microscopic observations, Figure 3a gives a schematic illustration of the failure mechanism for the sliding wear of SFRP composites

without nanoparticles. The transfer film formed during the running stage is mainly composed of worn matrix material and can effectively reduce the 'direct contact' of the composite with asperities of the hard metallic counterface [8, 9]. Nevertheless, the worn fibers are exposed to the most of normal load and shear forces during the wear process and slide often directly against the counterpart, which results in stress concentrations at the interfacial regions between fibers and matrix. Moreover, due to the frictional heating induced by the fibers, the temperature of the matrix around the fibers would be relatively high. As a result, with an increase in the pv factor, failure of the material occurs firstly in the interfacial region. When the matrix failed to support the short fibers, serious fiber removal could occur and thus a rapid increase in the wear rate. Finally, the material can no longer be employed.

For the nanocomposites, a three-body contact condition was induced by the additional nanoparticles between the contact surfaces. The presence of nanoparticles in the contact region is evidenced by the nano-grooves/indents on the fiber surface [6]. As illustrated in Figure 3b, many of the hard particles were embedded in the soft polymeric transfer film on the counterface and grooved the exposed fibers. In this way, the distance between the steel and the composite material was also enhanced i.e. the particle acted as 'spacers'. This, in turn, caused reduction in the adhesion between the contact surfaces. Therefore, the friction coefficient of the nanocomposites was always lower than that of the composites without nanoparticles. Moreover, as the nanoparticles were free to move, they tend to be dispersed uniformly over the transfer film during the wear process, which would result in a uniform contact stress between the contact surfaces and minimize the stress concentration on the individual fibers. As a result, the thermal failure of polymer matrix in the interfacial region between SCF/matrix was avoided and thus a gradual removal process of short fibers occurred. This ensured that the wear rate of the nanocomposites was stable at $\sim 10^{-6}$ mm³/(Nm) even under extreme loading conditions.

5 Synergistic Effect of Nanoparticles and TFLs on the Sliding Wear of Polymer Composites

With the use of solid lubricants i.e. graphite and PTFE, transfer film layers (TFLs) are usually

formed during the sliding of all the composites i.e. with and without nanoparticles, against steel counterparts [8, 9]. It was reported that the properties of the transfer films might also be influenced by the additional nanoparticles, which finally have an effect on the wear performance of polymeric composites [4]. In this study, we use a high resolution nanoindentation instrument to systematically evaluate the transfer films developed under different sliding conditions.

Figures 4 and 5 compare the indentation behaviours of the TFLs formed by two PA 66-based composites with and without nanoparticles, under the sliding condition of 2 MPa, 2m/s. As shown in Figure 4, an observable TFL was developed on the surface of the steel disk. As a result, the measured hardness is always smaller than that of the original steel (which is ~ 12.1 GPa). However, the notable variations of the load-depth curves indicate that the distribution of the TFL was not perfectly uniform. Such character of the TFL was also confirmed by AFM observations, shown in Figure 4b. The TFL did not fully cover the whole worn region. Some places in the worn area, e.g. indent 7#, are almost as hard as the neat steel. It is also noticed that the soft TFL could be pushed out of the indentation area and form a "pile-up" around the indent (e.g. the indent 6# in Figure 4b).

Figure 5 shows the indentation behaviour of the steel counterpart tested against the composite without nanoparticles. In this case, the measure hardness is very similar to that of the original steel disk, suggesting that there was no effective TFL formed in the worn region. The conclusion was also supported by the AFM image. As shown in Figure 5b, the size of the indents is much smaller and no pile-up can be observed.

It is clear that the additional nanoparticles were helpful for the formation of transfer films under the same sliding conditions. To further explore the relationship between the TFL and the wear behaviour of polymer composites, more indentation tests were carried out. It was found that TFLs were more likely to form with the addition of nanoparticles under all the tested conditions, especially under high pv conditions. Accordingly, the polymeric hybrid nanocomposites showed higher wear resistance (cf. Figure 1). As aforementioned, the low friction behavior of the nanocomposites was achieved by the mechanical interactions among the

nanoparticles This can reasonably explain the beneficial effect of nanoparticles on the formation of TFLs, since low friction coefficient could generally provide better opportunities for wear debris to stay in the worn regions and therefore to develop TFLs during sliding processes. On the other hand, the TFLs can partly cover the nanoparticles and minimize their abrasive effects. Therefore, there is a synergistic action in tribological performance of the polymer composites with nanoparticles and TFLs. Nevertheless, it should be stated that wear of polymer composites is very complicated, depending on many factors. To fully characterise the wear mechanisms of the synergistic effect of various fillers, a further study is still needed.

6 Conclusions

In this work, the wear mechanisms of the hybrid polymer nanocomposites filled with both nanoparticles and conventional micro-sized tribo-fillers were investigated. It was found that the load carrying capacity of the SFRPs is mainly determined by the properties of fibers. However, the tribological performance of SFRPs can be significantly improved by using nanoparticles due to their friction reducing abilities, especially under extreme loading conditions. In particular, the advantages produced by additional nanoparticles can be attributed to the following effects:

1. The adhesion between the contact surfaces was reduced with the presence of nanoparticles, due to the increased distance between the steel and the composite material i.e. the particles acted as ‘spacers’.
2. The stress concentration on the individual fibers was minimized with the dispersed nanoparticles in the contact region, which consequently protected the polymer matrix in the interfacial regions from the thermal-mechanical failure. This finally led to a gradual removal process of short fibers and the high wear resistance of the composites.
3. The additional nanoparticles were helpful for the formation of transfer films, especially under extreme sliding conditions, which results higher wear resistance of polymeric hybrid composites.

(a)

(b)

Fig.1. Wear results for the polymer composites: (a) the specific wear rate, and (b) the friction coefficient. Dashed lines: wear results for the composite with nanoparticles; full lines: wear results for the composite without nanoparticles.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Tilted SEM images with an angle of 45 degree for the short fibers in the worn surfaces of (a) graphite +SCF+PTFE/epoxy and (b) nano-TiO₂+graphite+SCF +PTFE/epoxy.

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Fig.3. Schematic illustration of the failure mechanism for the sliding wear of SRFP composites (a) without and (b) with nanoparticles.

Fig. 4 (a) Load-depth curves of nanoindentation tests for the TFL formed by nano-TiO₂+SCF+graphite/PA 66 under 2MPa and 2m/s, and (b) the corresponding AFM image of the indents, and the cross-sectional

measurements of the indents 6# and 7#. The values of measured hardness for 9 indents are 1.41, 1.21, 6.99, 2.4, 1.95, 1.9, 11.2, 8.2 and 8.85 GPa, respectively.

Fig. 5 (a) Load-depth curves of 9 nanoindentation tests on the TFL formed by SCF+graphite/PA 66 under 2MPa and 2m/s, and (b) the AFM image of the indents and the cross-sectional measurement of the indent 4#. The values of measured hardness for 9 indents are 16.1, 15.2, 10.8, 12.4, 11.9, 12.3, 11.5, 12.2 and 9.2 GPa respectively.

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